

IoT for H2O Watch: A low-cost real-time water level and quality monitoring system

I. Abstract

In Bangladesh, the public's health and the country's economic health are negatively impacted by the lack of access to safe and clean water. This paper presents a real-time, low-cost water quality and level monitoring and control system specifically intended for Bangladeshi homes. This system keeps an eye on essential water quality and level parameters like turbidity, pH, and ultrasonic while monitoring real-time data visualization and alerts. It is an equipment able to monitor in real time the incoming water flow to any house or residential building. Access can be made remotely through a mobile application. The tool allows the users to monitor the water level in their tanks and enables them to check undesired air flow in water pipes as well as leaks, leading to more efficient consumption. Users can also use it to verify the amount charged on the supplier bill. Therefore, **H2O Watch** helps encourage society to adopt more environmentally friendly water practices.

The Sustainable Development Goal 6 of the UN, which aims to ensure everyone has access to and sustainable management of water and sanitation, is also supported by this paper. By addressing the challenges contributing to improved water quality and sanitation access in Bangladesh and beyond.

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Internet of Things (IoT), water quality monitoring, water level monitoring, real-time control, Dhaka, Bangladesh, public health, water security

IV. Abbreviations and Acronyms

- A. IoT - Internet of Things
- B. H2O - Water

Introduction

Bangladesh faces a significant challenge in ensuring access to clean and safe water, impacting public health and economic well-being. In this context, **H2O Watch** - a low-cost real-time water level and quality monitoring system designed to empower Bangladeshi residents, particularly in Dhaka, to make informed decisions about their water usage and safeguard their health.

Methodology

System Overview

The **H2O Watch** is a low-cost, real-time water quality monitoring and control system designed to empower Bangladeshi residents, particularly in Dhaka city, to make informed decisions about their water usage and protect their health. The system can operate from smart devices (e.g., Phone, Tablet, PC), built around readily available sensors, open-source platforms, and user-centric design.

Required components for this project include:

1. Sensor

- Waterproof Ultrasonic Sensor (JSN-SR04T/AJ-SR04M)
- pH Sensor
- Turbidity Sensor

2. Microcontroller

- Arduino Uno WiFi
- ESP-01S WiFi Module

System Design

Circuit Diagram

System Architecture

Flow of Data

Flow Chart

Front-End Technologies

UI Design

Back-End Technologies

Entity Relationship (ER) Diagram

Testing Plan

I. Integration testing with web interface:

A. pH Sensor:

- **Focus:** Accuracy and sensitivity
- **Inputs & Expected Outputs:**
 - **pH < 6.5:** Alert triggered (simulated or displayed on web interface)
 - **pH 6.5 - 7.5:** "Normal" displayed on web interface
 - **pH > 7.5:** Alert triggered (simulated or displayed on web interface)
- **Assumptions:** Temperature = 25°C
- **Testing Environment:** WiFi connection, pH sensor connected to the Arduino and web interface.

B. Ultrasonic Sensor:

- **Focus:** Measure accuracy of water level
- **Inputs & Expected Outputs:**
 - **Empty tank:** Display should show "0%" or "Tank Empty"
 - **Partially filled tank:** Display should show a value corresponding to the measured water level (as a percentage or distance)
 - **Full tank:** Display should show "100%" or "Tank Full"
- **Assumptions:** The sensor stands above the tank's bottom at a distance that has been specified.
- **Testing Environment:** individual sensor connected to the Arduino and a separate distance measuring tool.

C. Turbidity Sensor:

- **Focus:** Response to varying turbidity levels
- **Inputs:** solutions that have different turbidity levels (e.g., clear water, slightly cloudy water, highly cloudy water).

- **Expected Outputs:** Sensor output reflects changes in turbidity levels (higher output for higher turbidity).
- **Testing Environment:** Sensor connected to the Arduino.

D. WiFi Module (ESP-01S):

- **Focus:** Connectivity and data transmission
- **Inputs:** Sending test data points and attempting to connect to a recognized WiFi network.
- **Expected Results:** A successful network connection and data point transmission.
- **Testing Environment:** ESP-01S module connected to a power source and Arduino Uno.

II. Unit Testing:

1. **Focus:** Sensor data acquisition, processing, and web interface/display output.
2. **Inputs:** Apply the proper techniques to alter the turbidity, pH, and water level in order to replicate real-world situations.
3. **Expected Outputs:**
 - The measured values from every sensor are accurately reflected in the web interface/display.
 - When pH and turbidity levels are abnormal, the system sounds an alarm (either simulated or displayed).
4. **Testing Environment:** Complete system setup with all sensors, Arduino, WiFi module, and web interface/display.
5. **Testing Process:**
 - Fill the tank gradually with water while monitoring the display/web interface for water level, pH, and turbidity readings.
 - Ensure that the displayed values are accurate and reflect changes in the Web Interface.

- Introduce solutions with varying pH and turbidity levels to ensure the system alerts for values outside the normal range.

Conclusion

Now we have completed three nodes in the system. We can measure ultrasonic values, pH values, and turbidity values in real-time for those two water treatment stages. However, we are still doing it using two water samples (pure water and muddy water). And the database is also updating at the same time when sensor values are updated. When considering the web application, the data can be easily retrieved, and tables in the web application are also real-time updated with the database. **H2O Watch** presents a promising solution for real-time water level and quality monitoring and control in Bangladesh. This system offers an affordable and sustainable approach to addressing water quality challenges.

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